

REVIEW ON THE RESTORATION OF MOUNTAIN ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPE

Viviane Beatrice BOTA^{1,2,3}, Gicu-Gabriel ARSENE⁴, Violeta TURCUȘ^{1,3}

¹ Department of Biology and Life Sciences, Faculty of Medicine. "Vasile Goldiș"
Western University of Arad, Liviu Rebreanu no. 86, 310414, Arad, Romania

² Doctoral School of Biology, Faculty of Biology, "Alexandru Ioan Cuza"
University of Iași, Bvd. Carol I no. 20 A, 700505, Iași, Romania

³ Department of Environment, Climate Change and Mountain Legislation, National Institute of
Economic Research "Costin C. Kirițescu"/Centre of Mountain Economy CE-MONT,
Petreni no. 49, 725700, Vatra Dornei, Romania

⁴ "King Michael I" University of Life Sciences of Timișoara,
Calea Aradului nr. 119, 300645, Timișoara, Romania

*Corresponding author: viviane.beatrice@gmail.com

Abstract

Many mountain ecosystems are affected by anthropogenic pressure and climate change. Ecological restoration is currently one of the main global efforts to conserve, but also to restore biodiversity, ecosystem services and improve socio-economic conditions. The extent of conservation efforts in Europe's mountain ecosystems is unknown due to a lack of synthesis of research in this field. In this paper, based on a review of studies published in the last ten years, we identify thematic research gaps, assess the database regarding restoration actions, highlighting both enabling and hindering factors for restoration success. We also summarize new socio-economic and technological approaches and solutions introduced in the field. We found that the number of publications on the progress in restoration of European mountain ecosystems is small, and those that do exist are geographically and thematically limited case studies. Most of the case studies focus on restoring forest ecosystems following extreme events, followed by hydrological restoration of rivers, peatlands and heathland habitats. There are few studies that address the role of fauna and indicator species in restoration. A limited number of studies address the issue of conservation policies, offering solutions and new methodologies. In the end, we propose some directions for future research in this domain.

Keywords: *restauration / ecological reconstruction, mountain ecosystem, mountain habitats, Europe; biodiversity; biodiversity conservation; ecosystem conservation.*

INTRODUCTION

Ecosystem restoration is one of the main global efforts to conserve and restore the natural environment and is defined as a process of supporting the recovery of a degraded, damaged or destroyed ecosystem through a wide range of approaches, from passive, with no direct intervention, to assisted or active restoration (SER 2002; Christman and Menor 2021). The urgent need for restoration action has also been underlined in official global commitments, including the *The Bonn Challenge* from year 2011 and the proclamation of the *UN Decade of Ecosystem Restoration*. It is important to highlight that restoration is not a substitute for the protection of intact ecosystems, but is a complementary strategy to conserve and restore biodiversity, degraded land (e.g. reforestation), restore, sustain and

enhance ecosystem functions and services, with socio-economic implications, and last but not least, to combat climate change (Di Sacco et al. 2021; Christman and Menor 2021).

Although globally, ecological restoration has been studied and synthesized in detail in recent years, and various restoration methods have been evaluated and compared, in the European region, and in particular for mountain ecosystems, the studies identified in the literature are specific, local, and limited to a few mountain ecosystem types, or address a specific restoration context. Even the review-type publications carried out so far on ecosystem restoration in Europe are few and are either trying to respond to the specific problems of a region, or are placed in a specific context. Gordon et al. (2021), evaluated the possibilities of using domestic and semi-domestic animals in rewilding projects to achieve conservation, economic and cultural objectives. And in the year 2023, Garcia et al. reviewed the literature on processes and ecological patterns of passive restoration with the aim of providing a scientific basis for the development of a management guide for ecosystem restoration in the Cantabrian Mountains (Spain).

To the best of our knowledge, there is no synthesis of scientific knowledge on the restoration of European mountain ecosystems. By systematically reviewing 149 search results and evaluating 32 original article studies published in the last 10 years, we addressed 3 key questions: What are the new research approaches and methodologies on mountain ecosystem restoration? When, where, and how is mountain ecosystem restoration research conducted? What factors promote or limit the success of mountain ecosystem restoration efforts?

It should be highlighted that the mountain area includes various categories of ecosystems and habitats such as: meadows (pastures and grasslands) with very different exploitation regimes and levels of biodiversity, forests, scrublands and shrublands, cliffs, ravines, rivers and streams, lakes, peat bogs, as well as areas of crop cultivation, more or less intensive tourism, areas of surface mining activities, various transport networks, etc. The mountain also represents the living environment for millions of people, for thousands of communities, each with its own history, its specific links with the components of the mountain environment, its plans for economic development, evolving in a global environment in which many constraints are manifest. Approaches to ecological restoration in the mountains are therefore different, from the scale of a peatland to the scale of a landscape, a watershed or a mountain range. Some ecological restoration actions (environmental restoration) are not necessarily the subject of scientific research and publications, but are technical actions applying the principles and recommendations of the theoretical sphere of ecological restoration; it is probably also for this reason that it is difficult to draw up a complete picture of ecological restoration in Europe's uplands, where about 81% of habitats are in a more or less poor state of conservation (European Commission 2022). In the media and NGO publications, success stories in the field of environmental reconstruction are highlighted as role models and arguments for possible funding/sponsorship for other similar actions.

In the European Union, a nature restoration law is still awaited, a first version having been proposed in June 2022, but which has also provoked heated discussions and opposition from members of the EPP (European People's Party - right-wing), who have set themselves up as defenders of farmers; numerous derogations and subsequent amendments have stripped the proposal of its character as "the most ambitious text on biodiversity in the last 30 years" (Lavocat 2023). In Romania, a country where "ecological

restoration" is still understood as the re-forestation of areas or the reintroduction of European bison, the Mountain Law makes vague references to ecological reconstruction, and only once, in Article 5 (8):

"The Romanian state will apply special measures for the planning of sustainable and competitive development areas such as concentrations where ecological reconstruction activities are carried out and the prevention of industrial waste production and water pollution, outside areas of tourist interest." (Law No. 197/2018 of 20 July 2018).

We do not know, at this date, the delimitation of these areas of sustainable and competitive development (presumably the reference is to economic competitiveness).

MATERIALS AND RESEARCH METHOD

For this paper, we consulted the Web of Science database using the key terms: *restoring mountain ecosystem, mountain ecosystem restoration*, with and without including the term *Europe*.

On the topic of mountain ecosystem restoration, 471 publications have been registered since 1991, of which 418 original articles and 23 review articles. A large proportion of these (303 articles) have been published in the last 10 years, of which 13 are reviews, and only two with reference to Europe. The majority of the articles fall, in descending order, into the categories Ecology, Environmental Sciences, Forestry, and Biodiversity Conservation (Figure 1 and 2).

For the purpose of this paper, we selected all Original Article articles published in the Open Access regime during the period 2013-2023, the most active period of publications on this topic. Out of the total of 149 results, only 32 studies were focused on Europe.

Fig. 1. Main categories with publications on mountain ecosystem restoration from 1991-2023.
Source: Web of Science database

Fig. 2. Main categories with publications on mountain ecosystem restoration from 2013-2023. Source: Web of Science database.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

a. Approaches in ecosystem restoration and conservation projects

On agricultural subsidies, a key element in EU biodiversity conservation policies, Merckx and Pereira proposed in 2015 a two-level approach to European agri-environment policy, based on the inherent fertility of the land and spatial scale: the first local, farm-scale level, worked intensively but sustainably with an emphasis on high yields; the second, in parallel, large-scale, low-productive land and protected areas, with ecological restoration in functional, resilient ecosystems. At the time of the study, about 10% of agroforestry subsidies were allocated to agri-environment schemes and farms in disadvantaged areas, including mountain areas, with the aim of conserving biodiversity by promoting low-intensity farming practices. According to the authors, agri-environmental subsidies for fertile land should support the implementation of measures beneficial to biodiversity while allowing, and even helping, to achieve high agricultural yields. Conversely, agri-environment payments for less-favoured areas for marginal land and protected areas should also promote restoration and management of natural succession. For this approach to be successful, a higher proportion of Common Agricultural Policy subsidies should be allocated to environmental objectives (Merckx și Pereira 2015). Recently, conversion of agricultural land has also been explored as a viable option for environmental restoration and conservation in sensitive areas. Granado-Díaz et al. (2022), analyse farmers' preferences towards partial or total reconversion schemes through a new methodology in a case study of the Mediterranean extensive farming system. The results show that farmers are willing to participate only on condition of considerable remuneration, on average 833 and 1187 euro/ha/year for partial and total conversion respectively. Heterogeneity of preferences was observed in terms of farm and farmer characteristics, management, attitudes and opinions on the objective of the conversion scheme. The authors consider that diversification of the rural economy and

environmental awareness campaigns are necessary for the success of conversion programmes.

In response to the weaknesses identified and the failure to limit biodiversity loss, new tools have been introduced in the EU's agri-environment policy post 2023 - the Green Architecture and the Eco-scheme, with new rural development programmes, improved cross-compliance and voluntary measures. However, more investment in biodiversity monitoring, knowledge transfer, strengthening of relevant institutional capacities remains necessary. Better design, transparency, involvement of farmers and scientists are also needed (Pe'er et al. 2022).

Two other publications address ecosystem services issues. It has long been recognised that the provision of ecosystem services can be severely affected by extreme weather events in the context of climate change. In 2016, Tomczyk et al. analyse the effects of intense precipitation events on the Gorge National Park (Poland). The results show that the provision of ecosystem services was affected, with impacts persisting for several years after the extreme event. Restoring supply trails requires considerable economic investment. Left to recover naturally, without human intervention, ecosystems suffered a biodiversity loss and restoration rates were low. The design and construction of trails can reduce the negative impacts of extreme events and contribute to the protection of biodiversity, as well as enhancing regulating services (e.g. soil erosion prevention). Results by Simion et al. (2023), show that the use of diversity indicators is a promising approach to increase understanding of the multifunctionality of ecosystem services (ES) in mountain regions and for operationalisation in land use policy and management. The approach allows consideration of the dynamics in the provision of multiple ES at different spatial scales, and highlighting the benefits resulting from interacting ecosystems as well as the unique contributions of ES from smaller areas to larger regions. While at the landscape scale, the provision of multiple ES is driven by structural heterogeneity and biophysical characteristics, at the plot level, the multifunctionality of ES is largely driven by the diversity of ecosystem processes and functions that determine the provision of individual ES. The authors argue that landscape policy and management needs to consider these scale effects and encompass the complex structural, functional and social aspects of ecosystems and their benefits. Ultimately, this will help to identify areas that should be protected, restored, or sustainably managed (Simion et al. 2023).

Solano et al. propose in 2021, a landscape dynamics framework for environmental planning and management and testing the effectiveness of protected areas in achieving the sustainability goals of the United Nations 2030 Agenda, using as a case study the historical trajectories of forest area transformation from 1936 to 2010 in the metropolitan city of Rome (Italy). Two dynamics have been observed, the first increasing fragmentation of forest cover in lowland areas; the second increasing forest area in inland sectors of the mountain landscape, mainly within protected areas. In lowland areas, the study highlighted the urgent need to establish new protected areas and rewilding areas, as landscape parameters are below sustainability targets for healthy forest ecosystems. The proposed framework can be used to test the effectiveness of environmental planning and management in other forest landscapes to achieve the 2030 Agenda targets. In 2022, Aasetre et al. introduce the concept of "boundary objects" in approaching ecosystem restoration projects by analysing the interface between science and policy in a case study of landscape restoration in the Dovre Mountains (Norway). Starting from the idea that ecosystem restoration as a management

enterprise involves communicative and coordination functions between actors with different positions and interests, the concept of boundary objects offers a new perspective in understanding the relationships established between them, analysing how actors from different backgrounds, with different interests and perceptions can be coordinated to achieve a common goal. The analytical concept can also be used to assess the direction and effectiveness of an ongoing restoration project.

b. Restoration of forest ecosystems and mountain meadows

A number of studies analyse and compare different ways of intervening to regenerate forests after an extreme event, such as forest fires, which have increased in frequency and intensity in recent years, affecting many protected sites (European Forest Fire Report 2022).

In climate-stressed sites, the main recruitment factors in forest restoration are the presence of a seed source and the availability of safe sites for germination, especially in harsh conditions after a forest fire. The literature mentions two commonly implemented post-fire management strategies, namely salvage logging and no post-fire intervention.

The study by Marzano et al. (2013) compares the effects of the two strategies in a burned area in the Aosta Valley (Italy), populated by *Pinus sylvestris*. Differences in species composition were found between the investigated treatments. Density and diversity of regeneration were positively associated with dead wood, except for *Populus tremula* populations, which regenerate vegetatively, behaving differently from other tree species. The strong spatial association of saplings with dead wood suggests that it produces microsites that favour the establishment of regeneration. The relationship between nursing deadwood elements and regeneration was found to be strongly anisotropic. In this context, post-fire management, particularly when removing burned wood, should be applied with an understanding of the effects on ecosystem capacity to recover, influencing both direct and indirect recruitment (Marzano et al. 2013).

In 2019, Marcolin et al. analyze the effect of 3 types of post-fire intervention on the regeneration of a mountain forest ecosystem. The case study conducted on *Pinus sylvestris*-dominated forests in the Western Alps, affected by fires with 100% tree mortality, shows that in case of severe fires, forest ecosystems can be deeply affected if their structure includes plant species without specific adaptations. It is important that the intervention is appropriate to the management objectives and restores ecosystem services. Post-fire salvage logging can negatively affect natural regeneration dynamics by contributing to hostile microclimate conditions through increased soil temperature and reduced moisture. The presence of dead wood, on the other hand, favours improved microclimate conditions for seeds. Cutting and releasing dead wood on the ground has a crucial effect on seed survival in the first years after fire. If there are no other hazards requiring specific management actions, the lack of intervention, with the preservation of dead wood, contributes to favourable microclimate conditions for seed germination and vegetation recovery. Cutting dead trees with the release of wood on the ground, at least partially, can also be a strategy to accelerate natural processes and increase the number of safe sites for regeneration (Marcolin et al. 2019).

In parts of Central Europe, especially in mountainous regions dominated by temperate mixed forests, the use of relatively low-intensity, uneven-aged silviculture is a common management approach because it mimics a less intensive intervention mode. As a result,

however, restoration of more severely damaged areas of the forest landscape has remained less researched. Diaci et al. (2017) synthesize research on the restoration of disturbed forests habitats in temperate forests in Slovenia and neighbouring regions of Central Europe where non-uniform forestry is practiced. The results show that active management aimed at favouring mixed non-uniform forests reduces the risk of disturbance and improves stand resilience. In contrast to those presented by the collectives coordinated by Marzano (2013) and Marcolin (2019), Dianci (2017) argue that salvage logging can have positive or negative effects on regeneration, depending on the method applied and the quality of the work. The main factors negatively affecting restoration are: lack of advanced regeneration and decayed woody debris, high altitude, steep slopes, dense ground vegetation and excessive subsidence. Planting or seeding should be applied in forests that have been disturbed, where many negative factors interact and where there is a high need for sustainability of forest ecosystem services (Dianci et al. 2017).

Quercus suber L. is considered a suitable species for the restoration of Mediterranean forests because of its ability to regenerate after fires and its economic importance in cork production. Several studies have focused on improving seedling quality and abiotic conditions at the planting site to favour the field performance of the species, but most have been carried out by independent testing of treatments. Neustupa et al. (2023), evaluated the combined effect of 3 reforestation techniques with *Q. suber* in degraded stands in the Mediterranean area: a nursery technique to support root system development, such as the use of deep containers promoting a longer taproot, combined with two field techniques - the use of tree shelters to mitigate solar radiation stress, and shrub treatments to reduce competition for soil resources. The results of the 2-year study show that the effects of the cleared shrub treatment overlap with the effects of using deep containers and tree shelters. Shrub clearing is the most appropriate technique to favour the introduction of a regenerating species such as *Q. suber* in ecosystems characterised by predominantly degraded shrublands (Muñoz-Rengifo et al. 2020). Although the study is not located in mountainous areas, the results obtained by Liva et al. (2013) show that the use of nurse plants in the restoration of habitats affected by the lack of regeneration of the characteristic species can be an effective method, less expensive than seed irrigation techniques and more environmentally friendly.

In Romania, Dobrescu et al. (2021) present a case study on the restoration of the historic garden of Peles Castle. The garden preserves a significant number of old tree and shrub species, and a high level of biodiversity, despite historical events and long periods of neglect. The paper deals with the challenges encountered in the restoration plan, which has to take into account the conservation of the natural aspect of the garden, the regular control and protection of specific species in the context of a new (tourist) function of the building, and the challenges of climate change. Similar challenges may also be present in other restoration projects, so the information presented may also be applicable outside historic gardens. As solutions, the removal of plants with low landscape value, degraded or invasive, and the replanting of all woody species affected by abandonment, with regenerative and resilient capacity, were proposed.

Dollinger et al. analyse in 2023 the rate and effectiveness of forest restoration in the context of climate change by combining field data with simulation models in a case study of Berchtesgaden National Park (Germany). This project aims to restore *Picea abies* forests from homogeneous to structurally diverse stage by mixing with *Abies alba* and *Fagus sylvatica*. In this case, both active, by planting, and passive, non-intervention conservation

efforts have been accelerated by climate change. The simulation showed overall achievement of targets by 2100, but forest composition remained an unattained target in all strategies tested. The slow pace of restoration underlines the need for action. Active restoration measures, such as tree planting, can bring the system closer to the restoration targets. The study also shows that passive (non-intervention) restoration can be a viable management option (Dollinger et al. 2023).

Historical ecology is attracting recent attention because of its potential use in developing new strategies for conservation and restoration of old-growth forest habitats by providing vital information on vegetation history and dynamics. The case study by Palli et al. (2023), focuses on montane forests in Pllino National Park, mixed *Fagus sylvatica* and *Abies alba* forests, prioritised in biodiversity conservation in Europe. Their results show a rapid colonization with fir during periods of low anthropogenic pressures in the context of socio-political instability, and an increase in forest and biomass areas following land abandonment during recurrent pandemics. The determinant role of anthropogenic activities over time in shrinking fir populations, and restoring ecosystems in the absence of direct anthropogenic pressures, is highlighted. The results also show the effectiveness of targeted restoration and conservation policies, and population monitoring as a conservation measure in the face of climate change. In recent decades, the abandonment of rural land has led to reduced anthropogenic pressure on ecosystems and expansion of forest areas, but the composition has remained profoundly changed from the ecosystem status of the past. Conservation projects that encourage the limitation of direct human activities help to restore ancient forests, biodiversity and give them an advantage (resistance, resilience) in the face of climate change (Palli et al. 2023).

More than just carbon sequestration potential, mountain forest restoration can offer a wider suite of benefits for society and biodiversity. In the context of intensifying climate change, coordinated action to restore mountain forests can provide urgently needed solutions to mitigate risks to infrastructure, rural livelihoods, food production, wildlife and recreation. Mountain forest restoration should be recognized as fundamental to conservation policy, economic incentives and land management decisions for high elevation regions (Watts and Jump 2022).

With the conservation of mountain pastures affected by declining livestock numbers and decreasing grazing pressure, Pauler et al. examine in 2022 the possibilities of controlling the invasive *Alnus viridis* species in Europe's mountain meadows. This species hinders secondary succession and afforestation, leads to loss of biodiversity, eutrophication of soil and water courses, affects landscape aesthetics, and contributes to greenhouse gas emissions. Normally, the expansion of the species was traditionally controlled by goat herds. The study shows that cattle, now bred instead of goats, while slowing the expansion of the species, cannot stop the process, avoiding consuming the plant. Engadine sheep are more suitable for removing *A. viridis* shrubs, especially if management objectives include forest restoration, because they consume *A. viridis* but not elderberry, a pioneer species in reforestation (Pauler et al. 2022).

c. Restoration of aquatic ecosystems

Restoration of aquatic ecosystems is considered an important step in achieving the goals of improving and conserving biodiversity, restoring fish habitats, and providing

ecosystem services (Hering et al. 2015). In Europe, aquatic ecosystem restoration projects are driven by socio-economic requirements and legislation such as the European Union Water Framework Directive (WFD).

Although this is an important issue, only 5 publications in the last 10 years address the topic of restoring mountain aquatic ecosystems in Europe. A 2015 study shows that in the case of hydromorphological restoration of rivers, the effects of measures on aquatic and floodplain-associated biota depend on the creation of habitats for aquatic organisms whose populations were diminished before restoration, sometimes to the point of extinction. The benefits are not necessarily related to the length of the restored river segment, so the authors recommend that restoration projects focus on improving habitat conditions (Hering et al. 2015).

Ventura et al. draw attention in 2017 to the need to conserve fishless mountain lakes through two case studies from the Pyrenees and the Western Italian Alps. Many mountain lakes, originally fishless, have undergone profound ecological changes following the introduction of allochthonous fish species (mainly trout and small fish used as live bait), leading to the reduction to extinction of allochthonous species (amphibians, macrovertebrates, crustaceans, etc.) and those adapted to life in large lakes. Species-specific studies are needed to assess conservation status, and urgent conservation action is needed at continental and regional level through legislation, and at local level through restoration and actions to stop the spread of invasive species. Restoration projects already exist worldwide, restoring mountain lakes to a fish-free state, with beneficial effects such as the gradual recovery of native populations being observed (Ventura et al. 2017).

Freshwater ecosystems in river floodplains are home to some of the highest biodiversity and are affected by anthropogenic pressure. For impounded water systems, resilience to changes in the natural flow regime is thought to be bidirectional, but it is unclear whether this resilience prevents the system from returning to intact conditions after the flow regime reverses. The study by Bau' et al. (2021), shows that the temporal inability of river floodplains to recover can be explained by the root dynamics of water-tolerant riparian plants. Their proposed model helps predict the impact of changing flow regimes on long-term river floodplain dynamics.

Mikuś and collaborators analysed in 2021 the changes in the ecosystem of the Krzcznowka mountain river in the Polish Carpathians following the lowering of a high check dam and the installation of several booms in the downstream reactor. Physical habitats, benthic macrovertebrates and fish species were analysed over the 5-year period of the restoration project. A fost observată o creștere a diversității taxonomice a macronevertebratelor bentice în relație inversă cu schimbările survenite în adâncimea totală a canalului, și schimbarea structurii comunităților de pești spre un stadiu natural. Metode de evaluare diferite au oferit rezultate diferite, astfel că se recomandă combinarea mai multor metode pentru a obține o viziune de ansamblu mai apropiată de realitate.

The increasingly degraded state of some dams and increased efforts to restore river ecosystems are increasing the number of decommissioning programmes. Although projects aim to improve the habitats, biodiversity and functions of riparian ecosystems in the long term, dam decommissioning could initially cause short-term negative ecological impacts due to the mobilisation of sediments accumulated in the reservoir. A recent study indicates that the effects of reservoir drawdown on stream biofilms exist but may be small and fade quickly (Atristain et al. 2023).

d. Restoring peatland ecosystems

Regarding the restoration and monitoring of peatland ecosystems in Europe, 4 case studies published in the last decade have been identified. The first study, by Nicia et al. in 2020, addresses long-term (200 years) changes in soil restoration following a landslide in the *Caltho-Alnetum* montane peatland of Babiogórski National Park, Outer Western Carpathians (Poland). Their results show that the landslide initiates a complex and long-lasting process of changes in the biological aspects of peatlands, such as the biodiversity of underground fauna and plant communities. Soil microarthropods represented by *Collembola* species are proposed as indicator species for the restoration process of mountain peatlands. They are considered a good indicator because in the process of natural regeneration of peatland, changes in soil structure occur, by restoring the saturated organic layer over the layer resulting in the landslide, and initiating the peat formation process, which negatively affects the abundance and diversity of the *Collembola* community (Nicia et al. 2020).

The second study, in 2021, examines the effects on the Forbonnet peatland in the Jura Mountains (France), restored following drainage at the end of the 19th century (Lhosmot et al. 2021). In the context that peatlands and related ecosystem services are sensitive to climate change and anthropogenic pressures, the paper proposes an interleaved multi-reservoir model that operates at different spatio-temporal intervals and is consistent with complex seasonal hydrological and physico-chemical responses in habitat outputs. The model has potential for long-term use in assessing and preventing other climate change impacts that are still difficult to model mechanistically in such mosaic ecosystems. Ecohydrological models of peatlands can benefit from such analyses of restoration programs. According to the authors, managers or researchers need to consider different levels in the study of hydrological responses due to restoration or meteorological changes (Lhosmot et al. 2021).

The study by Burliga et al. (2023), shows the effectiveness of combining LiDAR, CIR (infrared imaging), GPR (ground penetrating radar) and ERT (electrical resistivity tomography) based analysis methods in delineating the original extent of peatlands, with potential applicability in peatland ecosystem restoration planning. In the case study of drainage-affected peatlands in the Stolowe Mountains National Park in Poland, LiDAR-based digital terrain modelling (LiDAR-DTM) enabled the parameterisation of peatland physiographic features and the determination of peatland extent, drainage directions and potential waterlogging areas; CIR analysis enabled the classification of vegetation types and GPR surveying revealed the morphology, thickness and internal structure of peat deposits.

The latest study, by Neustupa et al. (2023), shows that low elevation ombrogenic peatlands are affected by peat extraction and severe acidification. In addition, the effects of climate change, such as decreasing snow cover and heat waves, lead to their frequent seasonal desiccation, indicating their transition to a different ecological state. Biomonitoring can provide insight into these rapidly changing ecosystems and identify key habitats for biodiversity conservation. To account for differences in strongly acidic habitats, the authors designed a desmid-based conservation value change index (NCV). Based on the analysis of peatlands in the Ore Mountains (Czech Republic), it was concluded that future conservation strategies should consider remaining peatlands and anthropogenic sites as habitats with relatively high ecological values (Neustupa et al. 2023).

e. Restoring mountain heathland ecosystems

Mountain heathlands are considered among the most threatened semi-natural ecosystems in Central Europe, but the effects of their restoration have so far been little studied. The study by Fartmann et al. (2022), focuses on the effects of heathland habitat restoration in the Rothaar Mountains on carabid beetle assemblages at different stages of restoration. Their results show a maximum of indicator species in the early and restored period. Overall, restoration measures encouraged specialist and threatened species, while generalist, non-specialist species predominated in the advanced stages of succession. Vegetation structure and microclimate conditions were key factors in the species composition of the species studied. Regarding the conservation of carabid beetle species, the authors recommend habitat rejuvenation by cutting and chopping grass in a mosaic fashion and at intervals exceeding two decades (Fartmann et al. 2022). Recently, a study was conducted on the potential for restoration of heathland habitats in the Cantabrian Mountains (Spain) using soil seed reserves in the face of current disturbances (inorganic nitrogen fertilization, fires, decreased grazing pressure). The case study focuses on *Calluna vulgaris*-dominated heathlands, and the results show that soil seed stock has the potential to regenerate these habitats following fire, playing an important role in maintaining the structure of specific plant communities (Alday et al. 2023).

f. Other studies

Study by Negro et al. in 2013 on the response of arthropod assemblages to habitat restoration affected by ski construction in the north-western Italian Alps. Soil, vegetation and arthropod populations in restored, unrestored slopes and adjacent pastures were analysed. Unrestored slopes are characterised by large tracts of bare ground and arthropods, regardless of altitude. Restored areas have higher vegetation and differences in arthropod population structure. The results show that spiders are the most sensitive arthropods, non-colonizing the slopes, and are indicator species of anthropogenically induced changes in high-altitude alpine habitats.

Diserens et al. discuss the possibility of repopulating forests in Poland and Belarus with brown bears in 2020, analysing their impact on habitat and possible conservation management challenges. A recent study from Romania focuses on the importance of small mammals as key elements in maintaining forest ecosystem functions. This group of organisms has a regulatory effect on vertebrate and non-vertebrate populations, a seed and fungal dispersal role, and a bioturbation role. The case study conducted in Romanian forest forests shows that the abundance of small mammals is higher at low altitudes compared to montane forests, but species richness is similar, and associated with tree canopy diversity, reaching maximum values in mixed forests. Small mammal heterogeneity was correlated with habitat heterogeneity as a whole. The results show the importance of the temporal dimension in designing research to estimate small mammal community diversity at both local and regional scales (Lazăr et al. 2021).

Only one study deals with the problem of air pollution, with negative consequences for human health but also for the ecosystem as a whole. The paper shows the potential of geoinformatics method based on Sentinel-5 satellite imagery combined with Google Earth Engine and GIS (Geographic Information System) for air quality assessment and analysis of

air pollutants in a case study of river basins and slopes in the Crimean Mountains (Tabunschik et al. 2023).

CONCLUSION

New approaches in the field from the review period include the use of the concept of "boundary objects" in mountain ecosystem restoration projects, historical ecology in the development of new conservation and restoration strategies, the design of ecosystem service trails with a preventive role in case of extreme events, the use of biodiversity indicators in understanding ecosystem services and their operationalisation in environmental management and policy. An increasing number of studies show the possibilities of using geoinformatics methods in ecosystem assessment and monitoring projects, with the combination of digital and ground-based instruments becoming almost indispensable.

The review of studies over the last decade shows that research on the restoration of mountain ecosystems in Europe is restricted to only a few ecosystem types and often deals with specific characters. Most of them concern the restoration of forest ecosystems, in particular post-fire intervention methods. Although the importance and need for conservation and restoration of mountain meadows has started to be recognised, this area of research is still under-explored. While a number of studies focus on the hydrological restoration of rivers, and the effects of dam decommissioning, little research is done on other types of aquatic ecosystems, such as mountain lakes, other water sources, and other effects of anthropogenic and climate change pressures. Progress is being made in restoring and monitoring peatland ecosystems, but the amount of research remains limited. Mountain heathland habitats, although highly threatened, remain poorly studied in terms of restoration processes. Isolated studies address fauna, semi-natural habitats and the effects of air pollution.

The mode of intervention must be appropriate to the management objectives, focusing on restoration of ecosystem services. In the case of aquatic ecosystem restoration, it has been observed that improving habitat conditions has priority over the size of the restoration area. The needs and particular features of the ecosystem, and the effects of the intervention method on the ecosystem's ability to recover, must also be well understood, as this can positively or negatively influence the restoration process. In the case of forest ecosystem restoration, there are several results in favour of assisted or active restoration interventions, but their effectiveness depends on the method chosen and the work quality. In some cases, the passive, no-intervention approach may be more effective. The differences between passive, active and assisted restoration approaches are poorly understood for other ecosystem types.

AUTHOR(S) CONTRIBUTION

Conceptualization, B.V and T.V; Data curation, B.V, G.-G.A and T.V.; Formal analysis, B.V., G.-G.A. and T.V.; Funding acquisition, T.V.; Investigation, B.V. and T.V; Methodology, B.V. and T.V.; Project administration, T.V.; Resources, B.V; Software, B.V.; Supervision, T.V. and G.-G.A.; Validation, B.V., G.-G.A. T.V.; Visualization, G.-G.A and T.V.; Roles/Writing - original draft, B.V.; and Writing - review & editing, B.V., G.-G.A. and T.V.

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The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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INFORMED CONSENT STATEMENT

Not applicable.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

REFERENCES

- Aasetre J, Hagen D, Bye K.** 2022. "Ecosystem Restoration as a Boundary Object, Demonstrated in a Large-Scale Landscape Restoration Project in the Dovre Mountains, Norway." *Ambio* 51 (3): 586–97. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-021-01582-2>.
- Alday JG, Calvo L, Rodríguez JLF, Valbuena L.** 2023. "The Soil Seed Bank Role in Mountainous Heathland Ecosystems after Fire and Inorganic Nitrogen Fertilization." *Forests* 14 (2): 226. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f14020226>.
- Atristain M, von Schiller D, Larrañaga A, Elosegi A.** 2023. "Short-term Effects of a Large Dam Decommissioning on Biofilm Structure and Functioning." *Restoration Ecology* 31 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1111/rec.13779>.
- Bau' V, Borthwick AGL, Perona P.** 2021. "Plant Roots Steer Resilience to Perturbation of River Floodplains." *Geophysical Research Letters* 48 (9). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021GL092388>.
- Burliga S, Kasprzak M, Sobczyk A, Niemczyk W.** 2023. "Geomorphometric and Geophysical Constraints on Outlining Drained Shallow Mountain Mires." *Geosciences* 13 (2): 43. <https://doi.org/10.3390/geosciences13020043>.
- Christmann T, Menor IO.** 2021. "A Synthesis and Future Research Directions for Tropical Mountain Ecosystem Restoration." *Scientific Reports* 11 (1): 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-03205-y>.
- Di Sacco A, Hardwick KA, Blakesley B, Brancalion PHS, Breman E, Rebola LC, Chomba S, et al.** 2021. "Ten Golden Rules for Reforestation to Optimize Carbon Sequestration, Biodiversity Recovery and Livelihood Benefits." *Global Change Biology* 27 (7): 1328–48. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15498>.
- Diaci J, Rozenberger D, Fidej G, Nagel TA.** 2017. "Challenges for Uneven-Aged Silviculture in Restoration of Post-Disturbance Forests in Central Europe: A Synthesis." *Forests* 8 (10): 378. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f8100378>.
- Diserens TA, Churski M, Bubnicki JW, Stępnia K, Pekach A, Selva N, Kuijper DPJ.** 2020. "A Dispersing Bear in Białowieża Forest Raises Important Ecological and Conservation Management Questions for the Central European Lowlands." *Global Ecology and Conservation* 23 (September): e01190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gecco.2020.e01190>.
- Dobrescu E, Cristina R. Mănescu CR, Georgescu MI, Stănică F, Tucă I, Petra SA, Toma F, Gâdea DM.** 2021. "Restorative Regeneration of Woody Ornamental Plants in the

- Historical Gardens of Peleş Royal Castle, Romania.” *Notulae Botanicae Horti Agrobotanici Cluj-Napoca* 49 (1): 12223. <https://doi.org/10.15835/nbha49112223>.
- Dollinger C, Rammer W, Seidl R.** 2023. “Climate Change Accelerates Ecosystem Restoration in the Mountain Forests of Central Europe.” *Journal of Applied Ecology*, no. February (October): 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14520>.
- European Commission.** 2022. European Forest Fire report: Three of the worst fire seasons on record took place in the last six years. Brussels, 31 October 2022.
- Fartmann T, Drung M, Freienstein M.** 2022. “Rejuvenation and Restoration Measures Foster Specialised and Threatened Carabid Beetle Species in Montane Heathland Ecosystems.” *Insect Conservation and Diversity* 15 (3): 348–58. <https://doi.org/10.1111/icad.12560>.
- García D, Suárez-Seoane S, Jiménez-Alfaro B, Álvarez D, Álvarez-Álvarez P, Álvarez-Martínez JM, Barquin J, et al.** 2023. “Renaturalización Pasiva En La Cordillera Cantábrica: Bases y Retos Científicos Para Una Sostenibilidad Socio-Ecológica.” *Ecosistemas* 32 (1): 2507. <https://doi.org/10.7818/ecos.2507>.
- Gordon IJ, Manning AD, Navarro LM, Rouet-Leduc J.** 2021. “Domestic Livestock and Rewilding: Are They Mutually Exclusive?” *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems* 5 (March): 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2021.550410>.
- Granado-Díaz R, Villanueva AJ, Gómez-Limón JA.** 2022. “Willingness to Accept for Rewilding Farmland in Environmentally Sensitive Areas.” *Land Use Policy* 116 (May): 106052. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2022.106052>.
- Hering D, Aroviita J, Baattrup-Pedersen A, Brabec K, Buijse T, Ecke F, Friberg N, et al.** 2015. “Contrasting the Roles of Section Length and Instream Habitat Enhancement for River Restoration Success: A Field Study of 20 European Restoration Projects.” *Journal of Applied Ecology* 52 (6): 1518–27. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12531>.
- Lazăr A, Benedek AM, Sîrbu I.** 2021. “Small Mammals in Forests of Romania: Habitat Type Use and Additive Diversity Partitioning.” *Forests* 12 (8): 1107. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f12081107>.
- Leiva MJ, Mancilla-Leyton JM, Martín-Vicente A.** 2013. “Methods to Improve the Recruitment of Holm-Oak Seedlings in Grazed Mediterranean Savanna-like Ecosystems (Dehesas).” *Annals of Forest Science* 70 (1): 11–20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13595-012-0225-0>.
- Lhosmot A, Collin L, Magnon G, Steinmann M, Bertrand C, Stefani V, Toussaint ML, Bertrand G.** 2021. “Restoration and Meteorological Variability Highlight Nested Water Supplies in Middle Altitude/Latitude Peatlands: Towards a Hydrological Conceptual Model of the Frasne Peatland, Jura Mountains, France.” *Ecohydrology* 14 (6). <https://doi.org/10.1002/eco.2315>.
- Marcolin E, Marzano R, Vitali A, Garbarino M, Lingua E.** 2019. “Post-Fire Management Impact on Natural Forest Regeneration through Altered Microsite Conditions.” *Forests* 10 (11): 1014. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f10111014>.
- Marzano R, Garbarino M, Marcolin E, Pividori M, Lingua E.** 2013. “Deadwood Anisotropic Facilitation on Seedling Establishment after a Stand-Replacing Wildfire in Aosta Valley (NW Italy).” *Ecological Engineering* 51 (February): 117–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2012.12.030>.
- Merckx T, Pereira HM.** 2015. “Reshaping Agri-Environmental Subsidies: From Marginal Farming to Large-Scale Rewilding.” *Basic and Applied Ecology* 16 (2): 95–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.baae.2014.12.003>.
- Mikuš P, Wyźga B, Bylak A, Kukuła K, Liro M, Oglecki P, Radecki-Pawlik A.** 2021. “Impact of the Restoration of an Incised Mountain Stream on Habitats, Aquatic Fauna and Ecological Stream Quality.” *Ecological Engineering* 170 (November): 106365. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2021.106365>.
- Muñoz-Rengifo J, Chirino E, Cerdán V, Martínez J, Fosado O, Alberto Vilagrosa A.** 2020. “Using Field and Nursery Treatments to Establish Quercus Suber Seedlings in Mediterranean Degraded Shrubland.” *IForest - Biogeosciences and Forestry* 13 (1): 114–23. <https://doi.org/10.3832/ifor3095-013>.

- Negro M, Rolando A, Barni E, Bocola D, Filippa G, Freppaz M, Isaia M, Siniscalco C, Palestini C.** 2013. "Differential Responses of Ground Dwelling Arthropods to Ski-Piste Restoration by Hydroseeding." *Biodiversity and Conservation* 22 (11): 2607–34. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-013-0544-y>.
- Neustupa J, Stastny J, Woodard K.** 2023. "Ecological Monitoring of Disturbed Mountain Peatlands: An Analysis Based on Desmids." *Biodiversity and Conservation* 32 (8–9): 2671–91. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-023-02624-9>.
- Nicia P, Bejger R, Sterzyńska M, Zadrożny P, Parzych P, Bieda A, Kwartnik-Pruc A.** 2020. "Recovery in Soil Cover and Vegetation Structure after Ancient Landslide in Mountain Fens under Caltho-Alnetum Community and Response of Soil Microarthropods (Hexapoda: Collembola) to Natural Restoration Process." *Journal of Soils and Sediments* 20 (2): 714–22. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11368-019-02434-z>.
- Palli J, Mensing SA, Schoolman EM, Solano F, Piovesan G.** 2023. "Historical Ecology Identifies Long-term Rewilding Strategy for Conserving Mediterranean Mountain Forests in South Italy." *Ecological Applications* 33 (2). <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.2758>.
- Parlamentul European, Consiliul Uniunii Europene.** 2000. Directiva 2000/60/CE a Parlamentului European și a Consiliului din 23 octombrie 2000 de stabilire a unui cadru de politică comunitară în domeniul apei. Jurnalul Oficial al Uniunii Europene, 15/vol. 6, 193-264.
- Pauler CM, Zehnder T, Staudinger M, Lüscher A, Kreuzer M, Berard J, Schneider MK.** 2022. "Thinning the Thickets: Foraging of Hardy Cattle, Sheep and Goats in Green Alder Shrubs." *Journal of Applied Ecology* 59 (5): 1394–1405. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14156>.
- Pe'er G, Finn JA, Díaz M, Birkenstock M, Lakner S, Röder N, Kazakova Y, et al.** 2022. "How Can the European Common Agricultural Policy Help Halt Biodiversity Loss? Recommendations by over 300 Experts." *Conservation Letters* 15 (6): 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12901>
- Simion H, Giombini V, Tasser E, Marsoner T, Vigl LE.** 2023. "Enhancing Understanding of Ecosystem Multifunctionality in Mountain Regions." *Ecological Solutions and Evidence* 4 (3): 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2688-8319.12265>.
- Solano F, Praticò S, Piovesan G, Chiarucci A, Argentieri A, Modica G.** 2021. "Characterizing Historical Transformation Trajectories of the Forest Landscape in Rome's Metropolitan Area (Italy) for Effective Planning of Sustainability Goals." *Land Degradation & Development* 32 (16): 4708–26. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.4072>.
- Tabunschik V, Gorbunov R, Gorbunova T.** 2023. "Unveiling Air Pollution in Crimean Mountain Rivers: Analysis of Sentinel-5 Satellite Images Using Google Earth Engine (GEE)." *Remote Sensing* 15 (13): 3364. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15133364>.
- Tomczyk AM, White PCL, Ewertowski MW.** 2016. "Effects of Extreme Natural Events on the Provision of Ecosystem Services in a Mountain Environment: The Importance of Trail Design in Delivering System Resilience and Ecosystem Service Co-Benefits." *Journal of Environmental Management* 166 (January): 156–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2015.10.016>.
- Ventura M, Tiberti R, Buchaca T, Buñay D, Sabás I, Miró A.** 2017. Chapter 8: Why should we preserve fishless high mountain lakes? In: Catalan J, Ninot J, Aniz M, editors. High Mountain Conservation in a Changing World. *Advances in Global Change Research*, vol 62. Springer, Cham., pp 181-205.
- Watts SH, Jump AS.** 2022. "The Benefits of Mountain Woodland Restoration." *Restoration Ecology* 30 (8): 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1111/rec.13701>.